

THE CAMIJR

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CROSS ABROAD MULTI DISCIPLINARY
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EDITORIAL COMMENT

It has been a long and tedious journey. To bring such a journal to life is indeed a grueling task but you never gave up. We have really proved beyond any doubt that with hard work, dedication and resilience nothing is impossible. Congratulations to all who, in diverse ways, have made this journal see the light of day. It has come to stay and do so forever.

As peace ambassadors, producing such a journal adds to your creativity and desire to reach out to the world. We have created a strong bridge that links you to the world in a strong and informed manner.

I encourage all to recommend this must-read journal to their institutional libraries. Simplicity in presentation and issues dealt with by the authors makes the journal unique, interesting and relevant to contemporary global challenges.

Peace to all readers, peace to the world.

Prof. Dramani Aminu

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FORWARD

Cross Abroad Multidisciplinary International Journal of Research, (CAMIJR) is a compendium of empirical and theoretical research works on varieties of educational issues across the world in relation to educational development

Our aim is to keep floating educative articles that will impact and Forster education for teaching, learning and sustainable development not only in Africa but in the whole continent of the world.

The editorial policy encourages an interdisciplinary approach involving humanities, social sciences environmental/vocational sciences, Technical education, Languages, Law, Educational Foundations Sciences etc.

We publish a well research work of any contributor irrespective of colour or race by annually. We selected about forty contributors on this first maiden edition of CAMIJR after through and careful vetting.

The editorial board of CAMIJR are delighted to consulting editors, Desk officer, from USA, Ghana and Nigeria and also our contributors.

We are also indebted to the people organization and agencies who helped in making CAMIJA a quality multidisciplinary International Journal of its kind. We pray to widen our relationship in content and in the world. We also encourage more contributors from Africa scholars across the globe

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**INVESTIGATING THE PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED BY FRIST YEAR
UNDERGRADUATE CHEMISTRY STUDENT IN LEARNING
CHEMISTRY IN UNIVERSITY IN SOUTH
EAST NIGERIA.**

BY

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Abstract

This study investigated the problems encountered by first-year undergraduate chemistry students in learning chemistry in South - East Nigerian Universities. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The study was a descriptive survey which was conducted in three selected universities of South - East Nigeria. The universities are Nnamdi Azikwe University, Awka. Imo State University, Owerri, and the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Simple random sampling was used to select the sample size used in the study. Three hundred first year chemistry students were sampled. Two instruments were used for data collection. The first instrument was Focus Group Discussion Guide (FGDG) which was used to generate the information used in building up the second instrument, titled Students Problems in Chemistry Questionnaire (SPCQ). The instruments were validated and their reliabilities established. An internal consistency of 0.85 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha Technique. The data generated from the study were analyzed using means and standard derivation. Z - test was used to test the null hypotheses at a significant level of 0.05. The results from the analyzed data showed that the students' level/state of readiness from secondary school chemistry were not adequate for them to comprehend first year chemistry course materials. It was found out that the instructional activities of their lecturers are poor and this factor contributes to students' poor performance in chemistry. The students, however, do not find their learning environment conducive for learning chemistry. It was also found out that good relationship exists between the students and their lecturers. Male and female chemistry students do not differ in their mean opinion scores on their readiness for learning first year chemistry course. Based on the findings, it was concluded that first year undergraduate chemistry students are infested with problems in learning chemistry. This implies that lecturers of first year undergraduate chemistry students should adjust their teaching methods to be a follow-up of the student's background knowledge to enable them comprehend first year chemistry course materials and also their environment should be enhanced by making available chemistry equipment and teaching materials for the students to have enough working tools. Among the

recommendations was that chemistry lecturers should be helped through seminars, conferences, support, supervision, and journal publications, to acquire a range of skills for effective teaching of first year undergraduate chemistry courses. Finally, the suggestions for further studies were stated.

Background of the Study

Chemistry is one of the most fundamental disciplines in the natural sciences that form the basis for technology in the modern world. The importance of chemistry as a science subject has tremendously grown since the first and second world wars (Olorunteghe and Oduyoyi, 2003). Learning chemistry as well as learning other sciences is, therefore, becoming more essential not only for the wellbeing of the individual but also for the society as a whole. Most modern-day creations of such technological developments have passed through the portals of science. To this extent, a country's strength can be taken as a function of the advances she is able to record in science and technology. There is no doubt that an undergraduate first year student of chemistry can contribute immensely to the process of acquiring scientific and technological capacities. Hence, undergraduate chemistry as a core science provides basic knowledge and understanding of the principles whose applications, with the aid of the teachers, will contribute greatly to the quality of life in a technologically based society. According to Felder (2002), first year chemistry students show high dropout and failure rates. They display poor class participation and are typically under-prepared. He went further to say that introductory courses are often designed for the prospective professionals with many topics treated superficially to provide a context for later study and with emphasis on structures. These structures may later serve as a framework for building a strong and well organized

understanding of the chemistry concepts. According to Seymour and Hewitt (2005) education through the knowledge of chemistry builds economy and forms pattern for human development. It moulds the bricks and builds the entire house, man and society in the areas of infrastructure, manufacturing, agriculture and medicine. Suffice it to say that the mainstream is chemistry because none of the above can be achieved without basic chemistry education.

Hart (2002) says that what students anticipate in their introductory chemistry courses depends critically on what they learn during the chemistry courses at their pre-university years. According to him, students expect to see a follow-up of their background knowledge. He asserted that when the previous knowledge of the students are not properly integrated into the new ones, it will affect whatever the content of the lesson the students listen to and what they ignore in the house of information provided during the typical course by their lecturers. When the previous knowledge is not adequate he further says, it affects what activities students select in constructing their own knowledge base and in building their own understanding in first year course materials. This, he concluded, could make the students display poor class participation which can eventually result to high drop out and high failure rate in their first year chemistry course. Leblane (2004) is of the view that to re-establish mental balance, a learner should bring meaning to new experiences through accommodation.

Furthermore, chemistry is a discipline for which a high standard of conduct must be amplified by teachers and researchers in ways that students cannot fail to observe and adopt (Spring, 2003). In consonance with this view, Old Father (2003) observed that effective science teachers demonstrate an understanding of facts, concepts and principles by robust explanations, giving of specific examples and reacting confidently and expertly to unexpected changes and directions during lessons, especially during practical classes. Students, he says, need to be equipped with the capacity for observing phenomena, capacity to think and capacity for reflections.

Unfortunately, some of the lecturers are too fast in lecturing students that some of the students cannot grasp anything during instruction. This discourages some students in learning chemistry courses in the universities. Umeobi (2005) added that rather than having behaviours or skills as the goal of instruction, concept development and deep understanding should be the main focus.

Oloruntegbe and Odutuyi (2003) pointed out that unqualified chemistry teachers, lack of textbooks, equipped laboratories, lack of journal and resources materials, contribute a lot to the problems encountered by first year students in learning chemistry in the universities. Most of the textbooks and journals in our libraries, contain obsolete information and, at times, are shallow in depth. Besides, chemistry teachers are not only few, but are also over-loaded with work that the teachers have no time for their lectures not to say anything about innovation and self-updating. These environmental factors affect the quality of chemistry taught to the students and

could lead to a high failure rate. Ifeakor (2006) opined that effective teaching occurs when a teacher decides what good practice is and observes the effects of his or her behaviours on students. Labiane (2004) is of the view that good teaching is as much as passion as it is about reason. It is about not only motivating students to learn, but teaching them how to learn, and doing so in a manner that is relevant, meaningful and memorable with their learning environment.

Much of what the lecturers teach in introduction classes for first year students do not seem to address this hidden curriculum, that is, dimensions of problems that are fundamental to first year undergraduate students' learning of chemistry which could be categorized thus:

- (i) problems concerning students' readiness to transit from their secondary school chemistry to university chemistry courses, in other words, how prepared are students (in terms of possessing requisite knowledge, skills and attitudes) ready to embark on learning first year chemistry courses, having completed the secondary school ones?
- (ii) problems associated with their understanding of chemistry during instructions by their lecturers and
- (iii) Environmental problems as well as students/teachers relationships which are related to their understanding in chemistry courses.

Statement of the Problem

The problem which this study addressed is what problem do students have in the four areas above that hinder their

learning and understanding in first year chemistry courses. In view of these factors, this study is conceptualized to investigate how such issues could affect the first year undergraduate students in learning and understanding chemistry.

Purpose of the study

Specifically, this study sought to determine:

1. the opinion of first year chemistry students on the adequacy of their state of readiness for learning organic, inorganic, physical and practical chemistry as introductory level courses in chemistry,
2. the students' perception of their lecturers instructional activities as a factor in their learning and understanding of chemistry,
3. the students' perception of their learning environment as being a factor for their maximum achievement in their first year chemistry courses and
4. how the kind of relationship existing between the students and their lecturers affects their general performance in chemistry.

Research Question

1. What is the mean opinion scores of first year chemistry students on how adequate they are for learning organic, inorganic, physical and practical chemistry as introductory level courses in chemistry?
2. How do first year chemistry students perceive the instructional
3. Activities of their lecturers, as in learning and understanding

introductory level courses in chemistry?

4. How do first year students perceive their learning environment as conducive for maximum achievement in the introductory level courses in chemistry?
5. What kind of relationship exists between the students and their lecturers as perceived by the students?

Hypotheses

The following four null hypotheses guided the study. They were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Male and female chemistry students do not differ in their mean opinion scores on their readiness for learning first year organic, inorganic, physical and practical chemistry.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean opinion score of male and female students on how the instructional activities of their lecturers impact their learning and understanding of chemistry.
3. Male and female first year chemistry students do not differ in their perception of their learning environment.
4. There is no significant difference between the opinion of male and female first year chemistry students on the kind of relationship that exists between them and their lecturers, as determined by the students.

Research Method

The study was a descriptive survey which was conducted in three selected

universities of the South-East of Nigeria. Simple random sampling was used to select the sample size used in the study. Two instruments were used for the study. The first instrument was Focus Group Discussion Guide (FGD Guide) which was used to generate the information used in building the second instrument titled Students Problems in Chemistry Questionnaire (SPCO. The part B set of these instruments was made up of four

sections which consisted of 40 items. The instruments were validated and their reliabilities established. An internal consistency of 0.85 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha Technique. Z - test was used to test the null hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. The mean score of 2.99 and below was accepted as indications of being one of the problems encountered by students in learning chemistry.

Results

Table 1: Z-test of the mean rating of male and female students on their understanding of chemistry (P<0.05)

Group	N	X	Sd	df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male Students	165	1.77	0.72	299	0.30	1.96	Accepted
Female Students	135	1.97	0.71				

This table shows that students had a mean of 1.77 and a standard deviation of 0.72 while female students had a mean of 1.97. When the Z-test was performed for the scores, a z-cal of 0.30 was obtained. This value is less than the z-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance (d/f = 299)

The null hypothesis is hence accepted. Male and female chemistry students do not differ in the mean opinion scores on the readiness for learning first year organic, inorganic, physical and practical chemistry.

Table 2: Z-test of the mean ratings of male and female students on the instructional activities of their lecturers (P< 0.05)

Group	N	X	Sd	df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male Students	165	1.89	0.74	299	0.15	1.96	Accepted
Female Students	135	1.73	0.68				

This table shows that the z-cal is 0.15. This value is less than the z-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance (d/f= 299). This led the researcher to accept the null hypotheses that stated that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female students on how instructional activities of their lecturers enhance their learning and understanding of chemistry courses.

Table 3: Z-test of the mean ratings of male and female students on the learning environment. (P< 0.05)

Group	N	X	Sd	df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male Students	165	2.26	0.57	299	0.32	1.96	Accepted
Female Students	135	2.05	0.76				

This table shows that the z-cal is 0.32. This value is less than the z-crit value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance (d/f = 299). This led the researcher to accept the null hypothesis that stated that male and female first year chemistry students do not differ in their perception on how the learning environment is conducive for their maximum achievement in chemistry.

Table 4: Z-test of the mean ratings of male and female students on the kind of relationship that exist between them and their lecturers. (P< 0.05)

Group	N	X	Sd	df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male Students	165	3.75	1.12	299	0.17	1.96	Accepted
Female Students	135	3.42	1.31				

This table shows that male students had a mean of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 1.12 while female students had a mean of 3.42 and a standard deviation of 1.31. When the z-test was performed for the scores, a z-cal of 0.17 was obtained. This value is less than the z-crit value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance (d/f = 299). This led the researcher to accept the null hypothesis that stated that male and female first year chemistry students do not differ in their perception on how the

kind of relationship that exists between them and their lecturers.

Discussion of the Result

On the adequacy of the students previous knowledge for comprehending organic, inorganic, physical and practical chemistry, their mean scores were below the midpoint of 3.0. The standard deviation of the items converged between 0.54 and 0.92. By this analysis, the students indicated that their previous knowledge of chemistry in secondary

schools was not adequate for comprehending first year university chemistry.

On the mean and standard deviation on teacher's activities during instructions, it was found out that all the items were below the cut-off point of 3 and above. By this analysis, the students indicated that the instructional activities of their lecturers did not enhance their understanding of first year chemistry course material. On the mean and standard deviations of students on learning environments, it shows that all the mean were below 3.0 and hence the students did not find their learning environment conducive for learning chemistry.

The mean and standard deviations of students' relationship with their lecturers as perceived by the students show that all the mean were up to 3.0 and above. Hence, a cordial relationship exists between students and their lecturers. Gender has no influence on students understanding and learning of chemistry.

Conclusion

It was observed that the identification of, and solution to, the problems encountered by first year undergraduate chemistry students would be a vital part of curriculum implementation that would help to reform chemistry teaching, support, encourage students learning and make them have favourable feeling towards chemistry. This study found out that the student's previous knowledge of chemistry in secondary schools was not

adequate for comprehending first year organic, inorganic, physical and practical chemistry.

Non-conducive learning environment and lack of in-built motivational strategies hinder students from learning chemistry. Generally, however, first year chemistry students relate very well with their lecturers but have problems with their instructional activities. An important aspect of this is that if these problems are recognized and solved, why should we not expect our economic development to be at its peak.

Recommendations

To avert the impending consequences from the on-going analysis, the researcher made the following recommendations based on the findings and it is hoped that if appropriately implemented, would help in improving the quality of learning first year undergraduate chemistry students acquire in chemistry in Nigerian universities and also bring reforms in teaching chemistry.

The following recommendations are made based on the findings

1. Chemistry lecturers should always encourage and motivate students to stimulate students' interest towards chemistry.
2. Chemistry lecturers should be helped through seminars, conferences, support supervisions and journal publications, to acquire a range of skills for teaching and learning chemistry.
3. Ministries of education, Science Teachers Association of Nigeria

and the state orientation agencies should ensure that students are satisfied with chemistry lecturers and emphasize the value of chemistry by liaising with the government to provide the necessary equipment.

4. Government should provide the universities with quality chemistry instructional materials and equipment. This is because teaching with instructional materials and equipment is likely to improve students understanding and learning of chemistry.
5. Qualified teachers should be employed in teaching senior secondary school chemistry to ensure that the students are fed with adequate chemistry knowledge for comprehending first year chemistry courses.

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that if these recommendations are implemented, first year students' problems in learning chemistry will be minimized and their understanding will improve. These reforms will automatically reduce the high dropout and failure rates in chemistry. Finally, the extent to which these teachers are well prepared, provided for, motivated and psychologically disposed will determine the extent to which we shall succeed in transforming from a backward technologically-backed to a vibrant economy.

References

- Felder, R.M. (2005). Trends in the first year experiences. *A report of an analysis of trends in the perceptions and behaviors of first year undergraduate students in seven Australian Universities.*
- Hart, D. (2002). A study guides for first year students. *A web page which often guidelines and lists expectations for first year student's University of Adelaide.* 13,8.105-107.
- Ifeakor, A.C. (2006). The status of resources for effective Teaching of Chemistry in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journals of Science teachers association of Nigeria 47th Annual conference.* 8-10.
- Igboko, K.O & Ibeneme, O.T.(2006). Effects of some cognitive constructivism instructional Approaches on students Achievement and Retention in the study of introductory Technology in Nigeria. *Journal of the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria.* 41, 1& 2.37-39.
- Leblane, R. (2004). Good teaching and delivery methods. The top ten Orequirements. *A paper presented after Professor Leblane won a Seymous Schulich Award for teaching Excellence.* Reprinted with permission of professor Leblane. 1-2.
- Newbury, N.F (2002). Teaching chemistry in tropical schools London: *London Oxford University Press.*
- Nnoli, J.N & Ikokwu P.I (2008). The educational implications for skill acquisition in meeting the visions of National Economics empowerment development strategies millennium development goals. *Paper presented at the school of Sciences Nwafor Orizu Colledge of Education Nsugbe 4th National Conference 8th -12th S.*
- Old father, P. (2003). *Motivating students -A responsive classroom culture when students do not feel motivated for literacy learning.* A presentation at the university of Georgia.
- Oloruntegbe, k.O & OduLuyi, M.O (2003). An innovative information and communication Technology (ICT) Based approach to thè teaching and learning Chemistry. *Science Teachers Association of Nigeria proceedings of the 44th Annual Conference.* 135.
- Seymour, E. & Hewitt, C. (2005). *Lack of student knowledge of career opportunities in chemistry.* American Chemical Society. 1-2.
- Spring, G. (2003). Expectations of research and information use competences in the undergraduate education in chemistry society. *American Journal of Research.* 3-4.
- Umeobi, C.I. (2005). Effects of constructivist Based Instructional Model (PEDDA) on students. *Unpublished MSc. Thesis, Unizik, Awka.*
- World book Encyclopedia volume 7. 82.